

Development of an Algorithm to Prevent Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injuries

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Background

- Hospital-acquired pressure injuries (HAPIs) affect ~ 2.5 million patients yearly
- ↑ morbidity, ↑ mortality, ~60k deaths each year
- >\$26.8 billion in annual healthcare costs
- 30-day readmission rate of 22.6% versus 17.6% (non-HAPI-related)
- ↑ pain, ↑ infection risk, ↑ length of stay (LOS)
- >17k lawsuits related to HAPIs annually

Problem

- Increased HAPIs in project facility despite reported use of evidence-based prevention strategies
- Clinical practices and views on HAPI prevention varies among nurses.
- Lengthy hospital policy and procedures for pressure injury prevention (~26 pages).

Purpose

To decrease HAPIs, evaluate the clinicians' views of HAPI prevention, and develop an evidence-based HAPI prevention algorithm to serve as a visual guideline for healthcare providers; hence, improving patient outcomes.

Method

- **Design:** Quality Improvement
- **Setting:** Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU) as pilot unit in an acute care hospital; Los Angeles, CA
- **Participants:** MICU Registered Nurses (RNs) as pilot group
- **Data Collection:** RN survey via Qualtrics pre/post HAPI prevention algorithm education, number of monthly HAPIs in the MICU

Framework

Framework: Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS)

Intervention

- **National Guidelines:** Recommendations from AHRQ were utilized to develop the pre/post survey. Project facility's policies and procedures were integrated to develop the HAPI Prevention Algorithm tool.
- **Anonymous Survey:** Evaluated responses on HAPI prevention; 17 pre-and post-surveys completed; Likert-like scale
- **Algorithm:** Developed a 1-page tool using evidence and project facility's policies and procedures.
- **Pilot Group:** MICU RNs recruited and educated via emails, Unit Practice Council (UPC) meetings, and staff meetings. Multidisciplinary collaboration with the pilot unit's UPC members, Clinical Nurse Specialist (CNS) and Wound Care Clinical Nurse Educator (WCCNE) to continually refine/update the HAPI Prevention Algorithm tool.

Discussion

- Preventative interventions to daily practice were impeded by time constraints.
- Pre-intervention, existing lack of awareness of current clinical practice guidelines and evidence-based practices.
- Post-intervention, the participants' responses moved towards the right directions.

Limitations

- Results limited to pilot unit; ↓ intervention fidelity, ↓ reliability, ↓ transferability.
- Unable to analyze overall unit responses since 45% of the staff from pilot unit did not participate in the survey.
- ↑ patient acuity in the pilot unit might be contributed to the recent HAPI incident.

Clinical Implications

- Lack of awareness of current care guidelines and evidence-based practices can lead to ↑ HAPI and ↑ patient harm events.
- HAPIs ↑ morbidity & mortality, ↑ LOS, ↑ readmissions, ↑ healthcare costs

Conclusion

- There was a gap between the use of evidence-based practices and nurses' responses to HAPI prevention.
- Anonymous surveys ↑ trustworthiness, ↑ internal validity, ↑ rigor, ↑ transferability.
- HAPI prevention was provided effectively and efficiently using a 1-page algorithm.

References

Email melaniecariker@gmail.com for references

Results

- Bolded survey questions showed statistical significance ($p=.048$, $p=.006$, $p=.040$).
- 50% decrease in HAPIs in the pilot unit, MICU.
- Compared to all NDNQI (National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators) participating medical centers, there was a 42% decrease in the pilot unit's mean, from 28.57 → 16.67.